

The Influence of the Pakistani Army on the Formulation of Foreign Policy: A Comparative Analysis of the Musharraf and Bajwa era

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Abstract

Foreign policies function as a structural design in the politics of states. Foreign policy is the insurance to maintain national security, the stability of the economy and establishes international relations with other states. While state institutions like the army, the judiciary, and the civil bureaucracy help and strengthen it. Specifically, the military supports the functioning of the state by defending borders and working under civilian governments around the world. But in the case of Pakistan, the army plays an important role in the formulation of foreign policy. Therefore, in this study, we examine the role and influence of the military in the formulation of Pakistan's foreign policy. The study will analyze the role of two military generals; Musharraf and Bajwa's role in the making of foreign policy. Furthermore, the objective is to examine the differences in foreign policies of the Musharraf government and the Bajwa era. However, the theoretical basis of the study will be Realism. The secondary literature available openly in the forms of books, journals, and media commentaries will be used for this short study.

Keywords: Foreign policy, Military, International Politics, Realism, international relations.

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